

Adaptive Inter-area Power Oscillation Damping from Offshore Wind Farm and MMC-HVDC Using Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—The coordination of the offshore wind farm (OWF) and high-voltage direct current (HVDC) links to provide ancillary power oscillation damping (POD) services may become a mandatory requirement from the transmission system operators in the near future. However, the performances of the POD controllers (PODCs) are vulnerable to the power system uncertainties and random communication delays of the wide-area signals. To address these issues, this paper proposes the design of the coordinated PODCs by using the deep reinforcement learning (DRL) method. The DRL-based PODCs employ one of the state-of-the-art DRL algorithms, proximal policy optimization, which can learn to adapt to the system uncertainties and time-varying communication delays by interacting with the power system continuously. A detailed simulation model of an OWF connected to the IEEE-39 bus AC grid via the modular multilevel converter based HVDC link has been built as a simulation platform, and the efficacy of the proposed DRL-based PODCs has been validated across a broad spectrum of operating conditions, disturbances, and communication latency.

Keywords—Power oscillation damping, offshore wind farm, modular multilevel converter, high-voltage direct current, deep reinforcement learning, proximal policy optimization.

ACRONYM

C-PODC	Conventional PODC
DRL	Deep reinforcement learning
GAE	Generalized Advantage Estimation
GSC	Offshore grid-side converter
GSMMC	Onshore AC grid side MMC
HVDC	High-voltage direct current
LPF	Low pass filter
MDP	Markov decision process
MMC	Modular multilevel converter
MPPT	Maximum power point tracking
OWF	Offshore wind farm

PLL	Phase-locked loop
PMU	Phasor measurement unit
PMSG	Permanent-magnet synchronous generator
POC	Point-of-connection
POD	Power oscillation damping
PODC	Power oscillation damping controller
PPO	Proximal policy optimization
PSS	Power system stabilizer
SG	Synchronous generator
TRPO	Trust Region Policy Optimization
TSO	Transmission system operator
WFMMC	Offshore wind farm side MMC
WT	Wind turbine

1. Introduction

The increasing integration of offshore wind farms (OWF) via the HVDC links will significantly change the characteristics of the onshore power system. In particular, many traditional synchronous generators (SGs) with damping capability will be turned off and the total system inertia will decline. As a result, the power system can be more prone to inter-area low-frequency (0.1~1Hz) oscillations [1]. To tackle this issue, in 2016, the European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSO-E) developed the grid code for HVDC and integrated OWFs, which requires the implementation of ancillary POD services [2]. Based on the fast-responding power electronic converters, the method of POD could be by active and/or reactive power (P and/or Q) modulation of the HVDC and OWF systems.

Numerous publications have shown that the damping of the inter-area power system oscillations can be improved by P and/or Q modulation of the integrated wind farms [3]-[9] and the HVDC links [10]-[18]. For the system that interconnects OWF and onshore AC grid through a point-to-point HVDC transmission, it concluded in [19]-[20] that the coordinated Q-modulation of the onshore HVDC converter and P-modulation of the OWF is more effective than individual Q or P modulation to damp the inter-area oscillations. Moreover, it has been found in [13]-[18] that the POD controllers (PODCs) are more efficient to damp the inter-area oscillations by using the feedback of wide-area signals rather than the local measurement signals because the former offers greater observability of the inter-area oscillations than the latter.

However, in real-world power systems, the wide-area signals sent by remote phasor measurement units (PMUs) suffer from stochastic communication delays, and the value may range from tens to several hundred milliseconds or more [21]. If the time-varying delays are ignored in the design of the PODCs, they can degrade the performances of the PODCs or even cause the close loop system unstable [22]. Most of the previous studies simply assumed the time-varying delays as a fixed value and then utilized a lead compensator in the PODC to reimburse the phase lag induced by this hypothetical delay value [17], [19]-[20]. However, the design of the PODC within this conventional approach cannot eliminate the adverse effects caused by the time-varying delays. Moreover, the power system operation condition, such as the generation levels, load levels, topologies, etc., changes frequently, while most conventional PODCs proposed in [3]-[20] are designed offline according to a given steady state and they cannot guarantee the optimal damping effects under variable operating conditions. Therefore, adaptive PODCs should be designed to overcome these issues.

Due to the high-order nonlinear, complex, and time-varying characteristics of realistic large-scale power systems, their full-scale mathematic models are difficult to obtain [23]. Thus, the measurement-based method and model-free method have been increasingly used in the design of adaptive PODCs. The measurement-based method [24] is to construct the simplified linear model of the concerned power system according to the real-time measured data that is set for system identification, and then design and update the parameters of the PODC dynamically. Authors in [24] and [25] developed the measurement-based adaptive PODCs for the HVDC link and wind farm to damp the inter-area oscillations, respectively, which can adapt to the variable system operating conditions. However, the robustness of such adaptive PODCs depends on the efficiency and accuracy of the online model identification of the power system, which may be subject to system disturbances and measurement noises. In this regard, the model-free method for designing the adaptive PODCs is receiving more and more attention, because it does not need the real-time identification results of the power system. Recently, adaptive dynamic programming (ADP) and reinforcement learning (RL) are the two popular basic model-free algorithms that have been used to design damping controllers for power systems. The authors in [23], [26]-[27] developed the adaptive PODCs for the HVDC links by using the goal representation heuristic dynamic programming (GrHDP) algorithm, in which reference [23] considered the variations of the system operating conditions and time delays. References [28]-[34] designed the RL-based damping controllers for the SGs to enhance the stability of the power system after severe disturbances, and some of them mainly focused on using the RL to handle the random delays of the wide-area signals [30-32]. However, these works do not consider the coordination of the OWF and HVDC to damp the inter-area oscillations.

Considering the powerful model-free optimization capabilities of the deep reinforcement learning (DRL) algorithm, we use DRL to tune the PODCs for the OWF and HVDC interconnected system to damp the inter-area oscillations. A detailed simulation model of an OWF connecting to the IEEE-39 bus AC grid via a modular multilevel converter (MMC) based HVDC link is built as a simulation platform, and the performance of the proposed DRL-based PODC (DRL-PODC) is tested thoroughly. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows,

- 1) The coordination of the OWF and HVDC for ancillary POD by using the DRL is first studied. The DRL-PODCs can not only adapt to system uncertainties but also the random communication delays of the wide-area signals.
- 2) Most of the RL algorithms previously utilized in the design of wide-area damping controllers [28]-[33] are only suitable for discrete action spaces and have large training variances. The proximal policy optimization (PPO) algorithm used in the design of the proposed DRL-PODCs, however, is suitable for continuous action space and has superior monotonic incrementality, ensuring training stability.
- 3) The advances of the DRL-PODCs are verified by comparing them with the conventional PODCs (C-PODCs) under various system operation conditions, system structures, wind patterns, and communication delays.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the coordinated POD control strategy of the OWF and MMC-HVDC interconnected system and describes the PPO algorithm for designing the DRL-PODCs. Section 3 presents the case studies and discussion to verify the superior damping performance of the proposed DRL-PODCs over the C-PODCs. Finally, conclusions are given in Section 4.

2. Methodology

2.1 Coordinated POD Control Strategy

Fig. 1 depicts an OWF connecting to the AC grid via the MMC-HVDC link, and the OWF and MMC-HVDC are incorporated with ancillary coordinated POD control. In this figure, the OWF comprises multiple direct-drive permanent-magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) based WTs with full power converters, and each WT is connected to the point-of-connection (POC) through a

box-type transformer (T_{ci}); The offshore substation is to house the step-up transformer T1 and export the power from the OWF to the MMC-HVDC via the submarine AC cable; The offshore converter station converts the AC power to the DC power and vice versa for the onshore converter station. The main items in the offshore converter station are the converter transformer T2 and offshore wind farm side MMC (WFMMC), and those in the onshore converter station include the energy dissipation device (EDD), onshore AC grid side MMC (GSMMC), and the converter transformer T3. The MMCs are composed of stacks of half-bridge submodules; The AC grid includes multiple SGs, and the angular speeds and phase angles of those SGs are measured by corresponding PMUs.

In this section, the variables with subscript ‘*ref*’ meaning the reference value, with subscripts ‘*d*’ and ‘*q*’ representing the components of the corresponding variable in *dq*-frame; The variables are in per-unit (p.u) unless otherwise specified.

Fig. 1. Diagram of an offshore wind farm and MMC-HVDC system connecting to the AC grid with ancillary coordinated POD control.

2.1.1 Local Controllers of the MMC-HVDC

The local controller of WFMMC controls the amplitude and frequency of the offshore AC grid voltage. Since it does not participate in POD, thus it remains unchanged and its details are intentionally omitted here, the readers are referred to [35]. The local controller of the GSMMC is shown in Fig.2, which uses the dual-loop proportional-integral (PI) controllers to regulate the DC voltage v_{dc} and reactive power Q_{mmc} . In this figure, u_s and i_s are the 3-phase voltage and current, respectively; θ_s is the measured phase angle (in rad) of u_s by the phase-locked loop (PLL); X_e is the total equivalent phase reactance; i_{cir} is the 3-phase 2nd order circulating arm current in GSMMC, which is suppressed by the circulating current suppression controller (CCSC) [35]; Δq_{pod} is the Q-modulation signal for POD.

2.1.2 Local Controllers of the Offshore Wind Turbines

The local controller of the machine-side converter (MSC) in each offshore wind turbine (WT) controls the DC-link voltage to the targeted value and the PMSG rotor current in *d*-frame to zero, which can be found in [6]. For the offshore grid-side converter (GSC) in each offshore WT, the local controller utilizes the dual-loop PI controllers to regulate the active power P_g and the reactive power Q_g , as shown in Fig. 3. In this figure, u_g and i_g are the 3-phase voltage and current, respectively; θ_g is the phase angle of u_g ; X_g is the equivalent total phase reactor; $\Delta p_{pod i}$ is the P-modulation signal that dispatched to *i*th offshore WT for POD.

the WTs modulate the output active power according to the dispatched signals ($\Delta p_{pod1} \sim \Delta p_{podn}$).

The effectiveness of POD is sensitive to the parameters of $\beta_p, \beta_q, K_p,$ and K_q . For the C-PODC, it employs the fixed values of them. In this study, we use DRL to dynamically tune those parameters in real-time to obtain optimal damping performance under system operational uncertainties and random communication delays.

Fig. 4. Diagram of the power oscillation damping controllers (PODCs), (a): PODC for P-modulation, and (b): PODC for Q-modulation.

2.2 Algorithm for Designing the DRL-PODC

2.2.1 MDP Formulation

The DRL algorithm tunes the parameters of the PODCs at a series of discrete time steps ($t = 0, 1, \dots, T$), and the time interval is set to 0.02s in this study. We model this control problem as a Markov decision process (MDP), where the major components are as follows:

1) State: At each time step t , the DRL agent receives real-time information s_t from the power system. We define the state $s_t = [\omega_g^t, \delta_g^t]$, where ω_g^t and δ_g^t represent the vectors of the angular speeds and phase angles of SGs measured by PMUs.

2) Action: the DRL agent updates the parameters of the PODCs to generate the ancillary P or Q-modulation signals for OWF or HVDC at every time step. We define the action $a_t = [\beta_p^t, \beta_q^t, K_p^t, K_q^t]$, and the parameters in a_t are in a confined region to ensure the action of the DRL agent will not deteriorate the operation of the power system.

3) Reward: Considering the average rotor speed deviation of the SGs is the reflection on the low-frequency oscillations in the power system. Therefore, a reward function is set to evaluate the performance of the DRL-PODCs, which is expressed as,

$$r_t = -\sum_{i=1}^M k_i \frac{H_{g,i}}{H_\Sigma} (\omega_{g,i}^t - \omega_{g,max}^t)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where M is the number of SGs in the AC grid; $\omega_{g,i}^t$ and $\omega_{g,max}^t$ represent the rotor speeds (in p.u.) of the i th SG and the SG who has the largest inertia at time t , respectively; $H_{g,i}$ and H_Σ are the inertia constant of i th SG and the total inertia of all the SGs, respectively; k_i denotes the weight of i th SG. By adjusting the weights, the targeted oscillatory mode can be chosen to be damped with high priority. It is worth noting that the value of r_t is equal to zero when all SGs are synchronized.

In this paper, we use the cumulative rewards \widetilde{R}_t from time step t until the end of the episode to evaluate the damping performance of a target oscillation, which is defined as:

$$\widetilde{R}_t = r_t + r_{t+1} + r_{t+2} + \dots + r_T \quad (2)$$

If the value of \widetilde{R}_t is lower (further below zero), it means the damping of the oscillation is weaker.

4) Policy and Value Functions: In DRL, a policy is denoted as π and represents a function that maps states to the actions that an agent should choose when it finds itself in those states. The value function of a state s_t under policy π is defined as the expected return when starting in s_t and following π thereafter:

$$V^\pi(s_t) = \mathbb{E}_\pi[R_t | s_t] \quad (3)$$

R_t is defined as the cumulative discounted rewards from time step t until the end of the episode:

$$R_t = r_t + \gamma r_{t+1} + \gamma^2 r_{t+2} + \dots + \gamma^{T-t} r_T \quad (4)$$

where the discount factor $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ weighs the significance of rewards obtained in the immediate future against those obtained in the distant future.

The value of selecting action a_t in state s_t , given policy π , is determined by the expected return that results from taking action a_t in s_t and subsequently following policy π .

$$Q^\pi(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_\pi[R_t | s_t, a_t] \quad (5)$$

The advantage function $A^\pi(s_t, a_t)$, which corresponds to a policy π , quantifies the degree to which selecting a particular action a_t in a given state s_t is superior to choosing an action randomly based on π , given that all subsequent actions will adhere to π :

$$A^\pi(s_t, a_t) = Q^\pi(s_t, a_t) - V^\pi(s_t) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 5. Training process of PPO algorithm for PODC

2.2.2 Proximal Policy Optimization

PPO is a policy gradient method developed from the Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO) algorithm [36]. PPO retains many of the advantages of TRPO, such as monotonicity improvement, and is simpler to implement since it uses the first-order optimizer. The PPO algorithm contains a policy function $\pi_\theta(s_t)$ and a state-value function $V_\phi(s_t)$, both of which are approximated by a neural network, where θ and ϕ denote the neural network parameters. The policy network is also known as the actor network, and the state value network is also known as the critic network. The structure of PPO and the training process for POD control are

shown in Fig. 5.

The training of TRPO is to maximize the ‘‘surrogate’’ objective:

$$\max_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_t \left[\frac{\pi_{\theta}(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{old}}(a_t|s_t)} \hat{A}_t \right] \quad (7)$$

subject to

$$\mathbb{E}_t \left[\text{KL}[\pi_{\theta_{old}}(\cdot | s_t), \pi_{\theta}(\cdot | s_t)] \right] \leq \sigma \quad (8)$$

where \hat{A}_t is an estimate of the advantage function at time step t , which can be calculated using the Generalized Advantage Estimation (GAE) method [37]. σ is a small constant parameter that is used to determine the maximum difference between the old and new policies. The expectation $\mathbb{E}_t[\cdot]$ represents the average value over a finite number of samples. $\text{KL}[\pi_{\theta_{old}}(\cdot | s_t), \pi_{\theta}(\cdot | s_t)]$ denotes the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between the old policy and the new policy. The constraint is to make the update of the new policy not much different from the old one. TRPO performs a linear approximation of the objective, a quadratic approximation of the constraint, and then uses a conjugate gradient algorithm to solve the problem.

Algorithm 1: PPO algorithm for POD control

input: Initialize parameters θ, ϕ ; batch size B ; entropy loss weight η ; $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \{\}$; λ for GAE(λ)

for trajectory = 1 **to** the number of trajectories **do**

for each time step t **do**

$$a_t = \pi_{\theta}(s_t)$$

 Execute actions a_t , observe r_t, s_{t+1}

$$\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \mathcal{D} \cup \{(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})\}$$

end

 Compute advantage \hat{A}_t and return \hat{R}_t via GAE(λ)

end

for each training epochs **do**

 Update the policy by maximizing the PPO-Clip objective:

$$\theta_{k+1} = \operatorname{argmax}_{\theta} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}|T} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{t=0}^T \min(u_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(u_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}_t)$$

 via stochastic gradient ascent algorithm.

 Fit value function by regression on mean-squared error:

$$\phi_{k+1} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\phi} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}|T} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{t=0}^T (V_{\phi}(s_t) - \hat{R}_t)^2$$

 via gradient descent algorithm.

end

end

To update the new policy without much difference from the old one, PPO uses a different approach from TRPO, which uses specialized clipping in the objective function, thus reducing the computational effort significantly. Specifically, the probability ratio $\frac{\pi_{\theta}(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{old}}(a_t|s_t)}$ is denoted as $u_t(\theta)$, so $u_t(\theta_{old}) = 1$. TRPO maximizes

$$L(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\frac{\pi_{\theta}(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{old}}(a_t|s_t)} \hat{A}_t \right] = \mathbb{E}_t [u_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t] \quad (9)$$

subject to the KL divergence constraint. This constraint limits the size of the updates to the policy, but it increases the computational effort significantly. PPO employs a modified surrogate objective that penalizes policy adjustments that steer $u_t(\theta)$ away from 1 to simplify the computational demands of the algorithm:

$$L^{\text{clip}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t [\min(u_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(u_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}_t)] \quad (10)$$

where ϵ is a hyperparameter, usually 0.1 or 0.2. Similar to the purpose of the surrogate objective, the term $\text{clip}(u_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)$ uses clipping $u_t(\theta)$ to suppress it from going beyond the interval $[1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon]$. To establish a lower bound for the unclipped objective, the minimum of the clipped and unclipped objectives is taken, resulting in the final objective. The training process of the PPO algorithm for POD control is presented in Algorithm 1.

Fig. 6. An OWF connected to the AC grid via a MMC-HVDC link.

3. Case Studies and Discussion

3.1 Description of the Test System

An OWF connected to the modified IEEE-39 bus AC grid via a MMC-HVDC link is adopted as the test system, as shown in Fig. 6. The OWF consists of 60×10 MW PMSG-based WTs, and it is represented by a single aggregate WT model. The WT model employs the two-mass drivetrain model and includes control systems for the pitch angle, MSC, and GSC. The maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm is utilized to optimize power output of the WT. The rated voltage of the HVDC is ± 350 kV, and

the nominal power of the GSMMC and the WFMMC are 700 MVA and 600 MVA, respectively. The GSMMC and WFMMC use the aggregate switching function model to represent each arm and include control systems described in Section 2.1.1. The AC grid contains 10 SGs, and each SG model includes the governor and the classic IEEE Type 1 Excitation system. The PSSs of SGs 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, and 10 are included, while those for SGs 4, 6, 7, and 9 are disregarded in this study. The whole system is built in MATLAB/*Simulink*, and the parameters of the WT, HVDC, and AC grid can be found in [38], while some of the data for the AC grid and HVDC has been adjusted and is presented in Section 7.

In this paper, PMUs are assumed to be installed at the busbars close to the SGs. They can obtain the phase angle and frequency of the busbars at a sampling rate of 100 Hz.

3.2 Design of the C-PODCs

The modal analysis of the test system reveals 2 inter-area oscillation modes existing in the AC grid without ancillary POD control, as shown in Table 1. The mode 1 has an oscillatory frequency of 0.81 Hz and a low damping ratio (3.7%), and it is selected to be the major target mode to be damped in this study. We use the residual method [39][40] to tune the C-PODCs for the OWF and HVDC, and the following basic criteria are followed,

- 1) The wide-area measurement signals that are selected as the input signals of PODCs should be the major participants on the targeted oscillatory modes.
- 2) The damping ratios of the other modes should not be decreased when the PODCs are introduced.
- 3) The damping ratios of the targeted modes should be improved as much as possible, and the changed eigenfrequency should not be more than 3% at the same time.

According to the above criteria, the parameters of the C-PODCs are determined as follows:

$$\Delta p_{pod} = 50 \cdot \frac{1}{\left(\frac{s}{62.8}\right)^2 + \frac{s}{31.4} + 1} \cdot \frac{5s}{5s+1} \cdot \left(\frac{0.05s+1}{0.02s+1}\right)^2 \cdot \Delta\omega_g \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta q_{pod} = 1.2 \cdot \frac{1}{\left(\frac{s}{62.8}\right)^2 + \frac{s}{31.4} + 1} \cdot \frac{5s}{5s+1} \cdot \left(\frac{0.04s+1}{0.02s+1}\right)^2 \cdot \Delta\delta_g \quad (12)$$

where the input signals of the C-PODCs for P-modulation and Q-modulation are $\Delta\omega_g = [(\omega_{g9} + \omega_{g10}) - (\omega_{g4} + \omega_{g6})]/2$ (in p.u) and $\Delta\delta_g = [(\delta_{g4} + \delta_{g6}) - (\delta_{g9} + \delta_{g10})]/2$ (in rad), respectively. Within the coordinated P and Q modulations, the damping ratios of the inter-area modes 1 and 2 are increased to 11.2% and 12.5%, respectively, which are more pronounced than with individual P or Q modulation.

Table 1 Inter-area oscillation modes without and with POD

Situation	Name	Mode 1	Mode 2
Without POD	Eigenvalue λ_i	$-0.19 \pm j5.1$	$-0.40 \pm j3.6$
	Damping ratio ξ_i (%)	3.7	11.0
	Major participants	SGs 9, 6, 4	SGs 10, 9, 6, 4
With only P-modulation	Eigenvalue λ_i	$-0.44 \pm j5.1$	$-0.50 \pm j3.7$
	Damping ratio ξ_i (%)	8.6	13.4
With only Q-modulation	Eigenvalue λ_i	$-0.27 \pm j5.2$	$-0.39 \pm j3.7$
	Damping ratio ξ_i (%)	5.2	10.5
With coordinated P and Q modulations	Eigenvalue λ_i	$-0.58 \pm j5.2$	$-0.47 \pm j3.7$
	Damping ratio ξ_i (%)	11.2	12.5

3.3 Design of the DRL-PODCs

To make fair comparisons between the effectiveness of the C-PODCs and DRL-PODCs, we choose the input signals and the parameters of the filters for the DRL-PODCs to be the same as those for the C-PODCs. In addition, the value of T_1 in the lead-lag compensators for the DRL-PODCs is consistent with the C-PODCs, which is $T_1 = 0.02$ s.

The DRL-PODCs are trained offline, and the DRL agent is interfaced with the concerned system model in MATLAB/Simulink. The simulation is repeated from 0 to 30s for each episode, and the networks shown in Fig. 5 are updated accordingly. A various of system operating conditions (i.e., short-circuit faults on different buses, load changes, $N-1$ faults, etc), and time-varying delays of communicating wide-area signals are considered in the process of training. It is important to recognize that the communication delay is caused by multiple factors, which includes the network delay, PMU reporting delay, and the time of transmitting PMU packets by using phase data concentrator. According to [41], the average time delay of communicating the PMU packets from substations to control center can be up to 476 ms. Therefore, to better simulate such communication delays, the minimum and maximum time delays used for training the DRL-PODCs are assumed to be 50 ms and 500 ms, respectively.

The hyperparameters used for training the DRL-PODCs are shown in Table 2, and Fig. 7 shows the variation in cumulative rewards during training. After training around 10000 episodes, the cumulative rewards of the PPO algorithm converged.

Table 2 Hyperparameters for training the DRL-PODCs

Hyperparameter	Value
Minibatch size B	64
Discount factor (γ)	0.99
GAE parameter (λ)	0.95
Actor network learning rate	0.0003
Critic network learning rate	0.001
Actor network hidden layer dimension	(128, 128)
Critic network hidden layer dimension	(128, 128)
The weight of i th SG k_i	$k_9=k_6=k_4=1.4 \times 10^5$; $k_2=k_3=k_5=k_7=k_8=k_{10}=6 \times 10^4$.

Fig. 7. Average cumulative rewards for each episode during the training process (the error bars are the 95% confidence intervals).

3.4 Simulation Verification of the Test System

3.4.1 Effectiveness of POD from P and/or Q modulations

The simulation in this section is to compare the efficacy of P and/or Q modulation, and the PODCs with parameters in (11) and (12) are considered. Under steady state, the OWF produces 600MW active power at the wind speed of 12m/s, the output reactive power of GSMMC is 0. The base active power and reactive power adopted in the simulation are 600 MW and 700 MVar, respectively.

During simulation, a temporary 3-phase-to-ground short circuit fault applies at the transmission line 16-17 near B17 at 10 s, and the fault is cleared after 240 ms. In this section, the dynamics of the rotor angle difference between the SGs (δ_{in}) is used to represent the target inter-area oscillation and $\delta_{in}=\Delta\delta_g$.

Fig. 8 presents the comparison of the damping performances without POD or with P and/or Q modulations. The results show the oscillation is weakly damped without the POD, and the damping of the oscillation is improved more significantly with coordinated P and Q modulations than with individual P or Q modulation. We use the Prony toolbox in MATLAB to analyze the frequency of the oscillatory mode, and the result shows that the dominant frequency of δ_{in} is approximately 0.76 Hz. The time-domain simulation results are in accordance with the previous modal analysis results shown in Table 1.

Fig. 8: The dynamics of the rotor angle difference between the SGs without POD or with P and/or Q modulations.

Fig. 9. Different scenarios of wind speeds.

3.4.2 Adaptability to Variable Operating Conditions

To test the adaptability of the PODCs to various operating conditions and disturbances, 6 different cases are considered, and their descriptions are listed in Table 3. Among these cases, there are 4 different scenarios of wind speeds included, as shown in Fig. 9. It is worth noting that Case I1 is the basic case, and the C-PODCs in (11) and (12) are designed based on this case.

Fig. 10 compares the damping performances of the C-PODCs and DRL-PODCs under Cases I1~I6. It shows that the two kinds of PODCs can improve the damping of the inter-area oscillations throughout these 6 cases. Since the C-PODCs are well-tuned

under the basic case (Case I1), their damping performance is almost the same as the DRL-PODCs in this case, as shown in Fig. 10(a). However, as the system operating condition and the disturbance change, the DRL-PODCs outperform the C-PODCs in damping the inter-area oscillation, as shown in Fig. 10(b)~(f). Interestingly, it shows in Fig. 10(d) that the suppression of the inter-area oscillation is more significant within the C-PODCs at the initial stage of the oscillation. However, subsequently, this oscillation is difficult to be completely damped out within the C-PODCs, and the DRL-PODCs work more efficiently on damping out this oscillation.

Table 3 Different system operation conditions and disturbances

Case	Operating conditions of the AC grid and disturbances	Wind Speed
I1	The load flow and AC grid structure are consistent with the basic case. A short-term 3-phase-to-ground short circuit fault (3-phase fault) applies at the transmission line 16-17 near B17 at 10 s, and the faulty line is tripping at 10.16 s, but it is reclosed at 10.4 s.	Scenario A
I2	The load L18, L27, and L15 are increased by 300 MW, 200 MW, and 300 MW, respectively, and a 3-phase fault applies at line 16-17 near B17 at 10 s, and the faulty line is tripping at 10.16 s.	Scenario B
I3	Same to Case I2, except that the faulty line 16-17 is reclosed at 10.4 s.	Scenario C
I4	The change in the load flow is the same as in Case I2. However, the 3-phase fault applies at the transmission line 26-27 near B27 at 10 s, and the faulty line 26-27 is tripping at 10.16 s.	Scenario A
I5	The change in the load flow is the same as in Case I2. However, the 3-phase fault applies at the transmission line 4-14 near B14 at 10 s, and the faulty line is tripping at 10.16 s.	Scenario C
I6	Same as Case I6, except that the faulty line 4-14 is reclosed at 10.4 s.	Scenario D

Fig. 10. Damping performances of different PODCs under various system operating conditions and disturbances, (a) Case I1, (b) Case I2, (c) Case I3, (d) Case I4, (e) Case I5, and (f) Case I6. The descriptions of the Cases I1~I6 are shown in Table 3.

For a more intuitive assessment of the damping performance of the target oscillation, with and without PODCs, Table 4 provides the cumulative rewards \bar{R}_t , as defined in (2), across the Cases I1~I6. Additionally, the table includes the percentage differences in \bar{R}_t between scenarios with C-PODCs or DRL-PODCs and scenarios without PODCs. For a specific case, a higher percentage value indicates a more pronounced improvement in damping of the target oscillation. Since the oscillation is triggered at 10 s, the \bar{R}_t is calculated from time 10 s to 30 s. It should be noted that the values of the \bar{R}_t may exhibit significant variations across different cases, depending on the rotor speed deviation in the presence of various system disturbances. Hence, the comparison of the \bar{R}_t is meaningful only within the same case. As shown in Table 4, the damping of the target oscillation is increased with both kinds of PODCs throughout the 6 cases. The \bar{R}_t of the DRL-PODCs in Case I1 is only slightly larger than the value of the C-PODCs, which coincides well with the result present in Fig. 10(a), because as mentioned earlier, the C-PODCs are well-tuned under this case. Apart from that, the \bar{R}_t of the DRL-PODCs has a more significant increase compared to the value of the C-PODCs under the other cases, which confirms that the DRL-PODCs can maintain optimal damping performance under varied operating conditions and disturbances.

Fig. 11 plots the dynamic response of the DRL-PODCs during the POD events under Cases I1~I6, which shows that the gains and phase compensations of the DRL-PODCs adjust in real-time to obtain the optimal damping performance, and the adjustments are varied in different cases. As the oscillation is damped out, the tuning of gains and phase compensations slows down.

Table 4 Comparison of the cumulative rewards under different operating conditions and disturbances

Case	Cumulative Rewards \bar{R}_t			Difference of the \bar{R}_t between with and without PODCs as a percentage	
	without PODCs	with C-PODCs	with DRL-PODCs	with C-PODCs	with DRL-PODCs
I1	-57.8	-46.8	-46.1	19.0%	20.2%
I2	-75.3	-52.0	-45.1	30.9%	40.1%
I3	-130.8	-96.5	-87.6	26.2%	33.0%
I4	-34.9	-29.7	-28.1	14.9%	19.5%
I5	-53.7	-40.9	-36.4	23.8%	32.2%
I6	-52.1	-43.2	-38.9	17.1%	25.3%

Fig. 11. Response of the DRL-PODCs during the POD events in Cases I1~I6, and the descriptions of the Cases I1~I6 are shown in Table 3.

3.4.3 Adaptability to Different Time Delays

We consider different kinds of time delays to assess the two types of PODCs, as shown in Table 5. For Cases II1 ~4 in Table 5, the system operating conditions and disturbances are consistent with the Case I2 in Table 3.

The damping performances of the DRL-PODCs and C-PODCs are compared in Fig. 13. This figure shows the DRL-PODCs can damp out the inter-area oscillation effectively throughout Cases II1 ~4. In contrast, the damping efficiency of the C-PODCs is reduced as the value of time delay increases, and they will even cause the system unstable if the time delays increase to the values set in Cases II3 in Table 5.

Table 5 Unexpected time delays

Case	Value	
	for Q-modulation	for P-modulation
II1	100 ms	120 ms
II2	250 ms	300 ms
II3	400 ms	500 ms
II4	With a stochastic delay, as shown in Fig. 12.	

Fig. 12. Stochastic time delay of the communication system.

Fig. 13. Damping performances of different PODCs under various time delays, (a) Case II1: time delays of Q-modulation and P-modulation are 100 ms and 120 ms respectively, (b) Case II2: time delays of Q-modulation and P-modulation are 250 ms and 300 ms respectively, (c) Case II3: time delays of Q-modulation and P-modulation are 400 ms and 500 ms respectively, and (d) Case II4: time delays of Q-modulation and P-modulation are stochastic.

Table 6 provides the cumulative rewards \widetilde{R}_t across the Cases III~II4, and the percentage differences in \widetilde{R}_t between scenarios with C-PODCs or DRL-PODCs and scenarios without PODCs. In this table, a negative percentage indicates that the PODCs adversely affect the stability of the power system, and vice versa. The system's stability deteriorates as the negative value increases in magnitude. It shows that the percentage value of the C-PODCs becomes negative as the time delay expands in Cases II2~II4 while the percentage value of the DRL-PODCs remains positive (above 33%) and changes on a small scale throughout the 4 cases. The results prove that the unexpected communication delays can have a significant impact on the performance of the C-PODCs, and the time delay can deteriorate the system stability if it increases to a certain degree (i.e Cases II2~II4). In contrast, the DRL-PODCs are adaptive to those time delays and can maintain superior damping performances.

Fig. 14 plots the dynamic response of the DRL-PODCs under Cases III~4, which shows that the values of β_p and β_q increase to compensate for the phase lag caused by larger time delays, while the values of the K_p and K_q decrease to mitigate the extra gain induced by the lead-lag compensators at the same time to obtain optimal damping performances.

Table 6 Comparison of the cumulative rewards under different time delays

Case	Cumulative Rewards \widetilde{R}_t			Difference of the \widetilde{R}_t between with and without PODCs as a percentage	
	without PODCs	with C-PODCs	with DRL-PODCs	with C-PODCs	with DRL-PODCs
III	-75.3	-53.7	-45.3	28.7 %	39.8 %
II2	-75.3	-95.3	-47.2	-26.6 %	37.3 %
II3	-75.3	-218.8	-49.8	-190.6 %	33.9 %
II4	-75.3	-76.1	-46.1	-1.1 %	38.8 %

Fig. 14. Response of the DRL-PODCs during the POD events.

Figs. 15 and 16 present the dynamic response of the offshore WTs, and Fig. 17 plots the Q-modulation of the GSMMC during the POD events. Since the P-modulation for POD relies on the kinetic energy of the WT rotating mass, it sees in Fig. 15 that the ω_d (difference in angular rotational speed between the PMSG and turbine blades) fluctuates during POD, but the maximum value is less than 1%. Generally, a smaller value of ω_d denotes the POD-induced mechanical stress on the WT structure is weaker.

According to the results presented in [8], such POD-induced mechanical stress can be acceptable for the safe operation of the WT. It is worth noting that the wind speed in this part of the simulation adopts Scenario B, which is larger than the rated wind speed (11.5 m/s) throughout the simulation time. Therefore, the active power of the WTs in Fig. 16 is controlled at the rated value of 1.0 p.u. without POD, and the pitch control is enabled to prevent the turbine rotors from overspeeding. To damp the inter-area oscillation, the WTs modulate the output active power (P_{wf}) and the GSMMC modulates the reactive power (Q_{mmc}) proactively, and the maximum range of the active and reactive power can be controlled to be $-0.1 \sim +0.1$ p.u. within both kinds of PODCs, as shown in Figs. 16 and 17. As the inputs to the PODCs utilize feedback from oscillatory signals, and the P-modulation of OWFs and Q-modulation of GSMMC can accurately track the corresponding outputs of the PODCs, the modulated active and reactive power will decrease as the oscillations are damped.

Fig. 15. Difference in angular rotational speed between the PMSG and turbine blades of the offshore WT (ω_d).

Fig. 16. The active power of the OWF (P_{wf}) during the POD events.

Fig. 17. The reactive power of the GSMMC (Q_{mmc}) during the POD events.

3.5 Discussion

For the OWF and point-to-point MMC-HVDC interconnected system, both the modal analysis and time-domain simulation results showed that coordinated P-modulation of the OWF and Q-modulation of the GSMMC can damp the interarea oscillation more effectively than the individual P or Q modulation. We designed two types of PODCs for P and Q modulations, which are the C-PODCs and the proposed DRL-PODCs. The design of C-PODCs used the classic residual method and they are with fixed parameters, while the DRL-PODCs utilized the PPO algorithm and can tune the parameters in real-time.

To comprehensively test the performances of the two types of PODCs, we considered different system operating conditions, including the $N-1$ faults, different load levels, different wind conditions of the OWFs, etc. In addition, the random time delays in communicating the feedback signals to the PODCs have been considered because those delays could exist in real-time implementation and affect the performance of the PODCs. The simulation results illustrated that both types of PODCs can damp out the target inter-area oscillation successfully under different system operating conditions and disturbances listed in Table 3. Nevertheless, the damping efficiency of DRL-PODCs was higher than the C-PODCs according to the indicators presented in Table 4. Moreover, the simulation results showed in Table 6 proved that the C-PODCs are vulnerable to communication delays, and they can even deteriorate the system stability as the time delay increases to a certain degree (i.e., the time delays for Q-modulation and P-modulation increased to 100ms and 120 ms, respectively). In comparison, the DRL-PODCs can maintain optimal damping performances under all the considered different communication delays, because they can adjust the phase compensation and the gain in real-time to adapt to these unexpected delays. During POD events, the OWFs and the GSMMC modulated the active power and reactive power proactive, and maximum adjusted values can be constrained to 0.1 p.u, which will not cause the overload of the power electronic devices in the WTs and HVDC converter. For each offshore WT, the P-modulation caused vibrations between the PMSG and turbine blades, but the maximum value of the vibration is less than 1% of the rated rotor speed, which has been proven to be acceptable for the safe operation of the WTs in our previous work [8].

Apart from the time delays, the communication network may also suffer from other data quality issues, such as the data packet loss and false data [23]. Therefore, how to maintain the damping performances of the DRL-PODCs under the conditions of the data packet loss and false data will be studied in our future work. In addition, to apply the proposed DRL-PODCs to actual

networks, it is crucial to ensure that the offline training model aligns with the practical power system model. However, the intricate nature of real-world power systems can lead to demanding computational requirements and lengthy training periods. Future studies need to improve the training efficiency and ensure the DRL-PODCs remain relevant and effective in actual networks.

4. Conclusion

The C-PODCs designed for OWF and HVDC have fixed parameters, and their inter-area oscillation damping performances are vulnerable to power system uncertainties and random communication delays. To address these issues, this paper proposes the DRL-PODCs for OWF and HVDC to damp the inter-area power oscillations. The structure of DRL-PODC is the same as that of C-PODC, but the difference is that the phase compensation and the gain of the DRL-PODC are tuned in real-time by employing the state-of-the-art PPO algorithm. As a result, the DRL-PODC can learn to adapt to the system uncertainties and different time delays by interacting with the power system continuously.

A detailed simulation model of a 600 MW OWF connected to the IEEE-39 bus AC grid via the ± 350 kV MMC-HVDC link has been built as a simulation platform. Various system operating conditions, disturbances, and communication delays have been considered in the simulation studies, and the damping performances of the DRL-PODCs and C-PODCs are compared by using the cumulative rewards \bar{R}_t as an evaluation index in this paper. The simulation results indicate the successful damping of target inter-area oscillations by both types of PODCs under varying system operating conditions and disturbances. However, the DRL-PODCs exhibit 4.6 % to 9.2 % higher damping efficiency compared to C-PODCs in most of these simulation cases. Notably, C-PODCs are found to be susceptible to communication delays, potentially compromising system stability when time delays for Q-modulation and P-modulation reach 100 ms and 120 ms, respectively, and the system's stability deteriorates as those time delays further increase. In contrast, DRL-PODCs demonstrate the ability to maintain optimal damping performance across different communication delays that range from 100 ms to 500 ms, and the damping improvement remains more than 33% compared to the system without the POD control. This adaptability arises from their capability to dynamically adjust phase compensation and gain in real time, ensuring effective response to unexpected delays.

During POD events, OWFs and GSMMC proactively modulate active and reactive power, with maximum adjusted values constrained to 0.1 p.u. This constraint prevents the overloading of power electronic devices in both WTs and HVDC converters. In the case of offshore WTs, P-modulation induces vibrations between the PMSG and turbine blades, and the maximum vibration is below 1% of the rated rotor speed. However, our previous work in [8] has proved that such vibrations are acceptable for the safe operation of WTs.

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7. Supplementary Data

(a) The adjusted data for the SGs and loads in the AC grid is as follows:

- 1) SG4: $H=38.6$ s; SG6: $H=44.8$ s; SG9: $H=74.5$ s.
- 2) $P_{L4}=5.0$; $P_{L6}=2.33$; $P_{L8}=5.22$; $P_{L15}=3.2$; $P_{L16}=8.29$; $P_{L21}=7.74$; $P_{L26}=1.39$; $P_{L28}=2.06$.

(b) The parameters of the excitation system for all the SGs are as follows:

$$T_A=0.001\text{ s}, K_A=300, T_E=0, K_E=1, T_F=0.1\text{ s}, K_F=0.001.$$

(c) The adjusted data for the MMC- HVDC is as follows:

- 1) Capacitance of each SM: 6.4mF (WFMMC); 7.4mF (GSMMC).
- 2) Rated active power: 600MW (WFMMC); 700MW (GSMMC).